

Phonological Domains --- Dutch

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Language name: Standard (=Northern) Dutch
Sources: G. Booij (1995) *The Phonology of Dutch*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
SIL (2005) *The Ethnologue*. www.ethnologue.com. (for the Language Profile data)
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I Language profile

of spks: 20 millions or more (all Dutch varieties)
Contact lgs.: German, French (neighborhood), Frisian (substrate), English (modern superstrate)
Status: official language in Netherlands, Belgium, Netherl. Antilles, Aruba, Suriname;
language of laws and policy in Indonesia (former colony)
Prospects: no shift, not threatened in NL and B, but decreasing in its importance in the Caribbean territories (shift to other languages as for instance Sranan)
Struct. results: lexical borrowings mainly from French (older), English (modern), tendency to simplification in colloquial speech esp. in phonology (as most other Germanic lgs. do)

II Morpheme types

derivational prefixes: [bə-], [ɣə-], [vɛr-], [ʔɛr-], [ʔɔnt-] (seem to be mostly unproductive, each has different meanings)
[ʔo:vər-] 'over-',
[ʔur-] 'proto-',
[ʔa:rts-] 'AUG',
[hɛr-] (different meanings),
[ʔɔndər-] 'under-',
[ʔɔn-] 'un-'

no inflectional prefixes

derivational suffixes: /-axtəɣ/ (final devoicing, glottal stop epenthesis!) 'ish',
[-ba:r] 'able',
[-dɔm] 'the set of',
/-heid/ (final devoicing!) 'ness',
[-lɪŋ] 'ling',
[-lo:s] 'less',
[-sxɑp] 'ship',
[-za:m] 'inclined to',
[-(ə)lək] 'able',
[-ənɪs] 'ness',
[-ər] 'er', (maybe /-ar/, see VII)
[-(ə)rəɣ] 'ish',
[-stər] 'er (fem.)' (and others),
[-tə] 'ness',
[-tjə] 'DIM' (with a lot of allomorphs depending mostly on the last segment of the stem, see III)

inflectional suffixes: e.g. [-ə] 'F.SG'/'ATTR',
[-ən] 'PL',
/-ənd/ (final devoicing!) 'PTCP.PRES',
[-də] ~ [-tə] / [-son, -voiced]+___ 'PT'
...

derivational circumfixes: [ɣə-tə] 'denominal collective'

inflectional circumfixes: [ɣə-ən], /ɣə-d/ (final devoicing) ~ /ɣə-t/ / ___+X₀ⁿ[-son, -voiced]+___ 'PTCP.PT'

clitics/particles: weak forms of function words are cliticized, no grammatical clitics

ablaut: strong verbs form PT and PTCP.PT by ablaut (and maybe affixes)

III Syllable

Syllable structure

- Pwords cannot end in short lax vowels except schwa.
- Booij says, that all syllables have to contain at least two morae, so that consonants in VCV-sequences are analysed to be ambisyllabic (there are no words with a monomoraic syllable followed by a vowel-initial syllable, thus CV.V(V)C is barred).
- Pword-initially, onsetless syllables cannot occur, therefore a glottal stop has to be inserted. Word-internally, onsetless syllables are always unstressed. So the glottal stop insertion rule has the foot as its domain (inserted before foot-initial vowels).

No onset (maybe other rhyme shapes are possible, but no examples were found):

VV	(fá:) _σ (ra:) _σ (o:) _σ	'pharaoh'
VC	(xá:) _σ (ʊs) _σ	'chaos'

1 consonant in onset (* /ŋ/):

CV	(ma) _σ (fə) _σ	'mad (inflected form)'
CVV	(nəu) _σ	'narrow'
CVC	(maf) _σ	'mad'
CVVC	(ka:s) _σ	'cheese'
CVCC	(hant) _σ	'hand'

2 consonants in onset:

CCV	(tra:n) _σ (tjə) _σ	'tear.DIM'
CCVV	(twe:) _σ	'two'
CCVC	(vlas) _σ	'flax'
CCVVC	(ɣraf) _σ	'graph'
CCVCC	(vrint) _σ	'friend'

3 consonants in onset (the first has always to be [s], the latter two can only be /p/, /pr/, /tr/, /kl/, /kr/, /xr/):

CCCV	(skri) _σ (ba:) _σ	'scribe'
CCCVV	(ʔɛk) _σ (stra:) _σ	'extra'
CCVCV	(split) _σ	'split'
CCCVVC	(stro:m) _σ	'stream'
CCCVCC	(sprɪŋk) _σ (ha:n) _σ	'grasshopper'

Appendices: A pword-final syllable can have additionally up to three coronal obstruents at the end.

With 3 appendix consonants, only [tst] (underlying /dst/, /tst/) is possible, but usually the first [t] is not pronounced!

(prɒmp-(t)st) _σ	/prɒmp+st/	'most prompt'
(vɛr) _σ (mu:j-(t)st) _σ	/vɛrmujd+st/	'most tired'

With 2 appendix consonants:

(ko:r-ts) _σ	/ko:rts/	'fever'
(ʔɛrn-st) _σ	/ɛrnst/	'seriousness'

With 1 appendix consonant:

(ʔe:) _σ (vər-t) _σ	/e:vərt/	'id.' (a Christian name)
(ko:r-t) _σ	/ko:rd/	'cord'
(ka:r-s) _σ	/ka:rs/	'candle'
(la:r-s) _σ	/la:rz/	'boot'

VV containing syllables

VV can either be a long vowel or a diphthong:

[ɣraf]	'graph'
[nəu]	'narrow'

Monomoraic words

There are underlying monomoraic words, but stressed short high vowels are lengthened.

/ku/ → [ku:] 'cow'

(In some southern dialects this word has a glide as its coda: [kuj].)

Thus, generally, monomoraic words do not occur.

Vowel-initial words

Words cannot be vowel-initial. If this is the case in the underlying form, a glottal stop is epentheticized.

Polysyllabic morphemes

Native monomorphemic words contain only up to two syllables, but loans can have more:

(ʔa)_o(pəl)_o 'apple'

(ʔəm)_o(ni)_o(bus)_o 'bus' (lat. loan)

(ka)_o(ta)_o(stro:)_o(fə)_o 'catastrophy' (gr. loan)

Phonotactics

[ŋ] is barred pword-initially, but allowed syllable-initially (but there it is analyzed as ambisyllabic and thus not really syllable-initial (Booij 1995:36)!):

[(ʔε)_oŋ(ə)]_o 'angel'

[t] and [d] are avoided pword-initially, but at least the first is allowed word-medially:

[ʔatlas] 'atlas' (syllabification unclear...)

The sequence [rər] is excluded. If a stem ends in [r] and a suffix /-ər.../ should be attached, an allomorph /-dər.../ is used instead:

/bitər+ər/ → [bitərdər] 'more bitter'

All other phonotactic constraints are segmental co-occurrence constraints or syllable-based constraints.

Superheavy syllables

Yes, but only at the right edge of pwords (cf. Hall).

However, there is some trouble about diminutive forms. Maybe the DIM-suffix /-tjə/ does not form a common pword with its host (unlike Booij 1995:111), but it cannot be a pword itself, because of the Schwa-constraint (pwords cannot have schwa as their only nucleus). However, there are allomorphs of the DIM-suffix depending on the last segment and the syllable structure of the stem to which it is attached. Thus, words like [ri:m+pjə] can be syllabified as [.ri:m.pjə.], or even [.ri:mpjə.] with a superheavy syllable that would be (following Booij) pword-internally, because a part of the syllable does belong to the suffix.

So maybe the domain for the following rules is the pphrase rather than the pword.

/-tjə/ → [-pjə] / VVm+___, CV(-stressed)(l)m+___
→ [-kjə] / VVŋ+___, CV(-stressed)ŋ+___
→ [-jə] / VV[-son]+___
→ [-ətjə] / .CV[+son,+cons]+___ (stress is very important here!)
→ [-tjə] / elsewhere

[ri:m-pjə] 'belt.DIM'
[hɛlm-pjə] 'helmet.DIM'
[ˈpəlɪŋ-kjə] 'eel.DIM'
[hɛk-jə] 'gate.DIM'
[təʃ-jə] 'bag.DIM' (stem: /tas/)
[bɒm-ətjə] 'bomb.DIM'
[pæn-ətjə] 'pan.DIM'
[stɛr-ətjə] 'star.DIM'
[tra:n-tjə] 'tear.DIM'
[by:r-tjə] 'neighbour.DIM'
[dɪŋki##təj-tjə] 'Dinky-Toy.DIM' (I've found no other examples with final /j/.)

IV Tone & Stress

Tone

There is no evidence for distinctive tone in Dutch.

Primary stress

Three different patterns, depending on the source of the word:

Germanic (inherited) pattern: always the first syllable with a full vowel

[.ˈpɛi.lər.] 'pillar'
[.bə.ˈvɛl.] 'command'

French pattern: always the last syllable with a full vowel

[.ka.nən.] 'gun'
[.pa.ra.də.] 'parade'

Latin pattern: the penultimate syllable if it is heavy, otherwise the antepenultimate syllable

[.ˈka.nən.] 'canon'
[.ˈva.li.ɪm.] 'valium'

Secondary stress

The normal stress pattern of Dutch is alternating. The normal foot is (σ)_φ. This causes a secondary stress in trisyllabic words either on the last syllable if primary stress is on the first or vice versa. (Of course, similar rules apply with words containing more than three syllables → 'σσ,σσ / ,σσ'σσ / σ,σσ'σ and so on.) But there are also other foot types: [ˌfoː.no.lo.ˈɣi:] 'phonology'.

Polymorphemic forms

Some native grammatical prefixes (and the pre-part of circumfixes) contain schwa as their only vowel. They can never be stressed. But there are also prefixes that are never stressed. All those are the only real prefixes, but do not belong to the host pword. They form a pphrase with their host, but do not belong to any pword themselves (as it is in German).

[.bə+.ˈvɛl.] 'command'
[.vɛr+.ˈtrəu.] 'trust.INF'

Most native "prefixes" have main stress of the whole word, but they have a stress pattern even when standing alone, and they can have appendices, what is normally only possible with pwords. So they form pwords themselves.

[.ˈʔoː.vər+.,gən.] 'transition'
[.ˈʔaːrts+.,va.dər.] 'patriarch'

Nativized former non-native prefixes (those which can be attached to native stems) behave exactly like compounds (and like the stressed native "prefixes") and get the main stress of the word.

[.ˈmɛ.ta+.,taːl] 'metalanguage'

Non-native prefixes lost their transparency and thus their possibility to get the main stress of the word. They form one pword with their host and get a secondary stress, if the host has no stress on the first syllable. The vowel reduction of unstressed short vowels to schwa can also apply, as much as the glide insertion, when two vowels meet. So I think, that they are not really prefixes, but part of the stem.

[.re.prə.sən.ˈteːr.] 'represent.INF'
[.rə.ˈdɪk.si.] 'reduction'
[.re.ja.ˈɣeːr.] 'react.INF'

In compounds, each part keeps its own stress pattern, but two adjacent stressed syllables within a pphrase are disliked. Usually, the first part of a compound gets the main stress of the whole thing.

[.ˈdɔrp.] ˈvillage'
 [ˈdoː.mi.,neː.] ˈparson'
 but:
 [ˈdɔrps.doː.mi.'neː.] ˈvillage parson'
 (the main stress of the second part shifts to the former secondary stressed syllable)

There are a lot of counterexamples:

[ˈhʊlp.,roː.bət.] ˈ(lit.) help robot'

And there are examples where the main stress is on the second part of a phrase (not compounds!) and the accent of the first word shifts:

[.nøː.'tra:l.] ˈneutral'
 [ˈʔɔp.stɛ.lɪŋ.] ˈposition'
 but:
 [ˌnøː.trɑː.lə##'ʔɔp.stɛ.lɪŋ.] ˈneutral position'

So stress seems to be a phenomenon of pphrases rather than pwords.

Inflectional affixes do not bear their own stress, whereas some derivational suffixes have a stressed syllable (non-cohering suffixes):

/-.,ʔax.təy./ ˈ-ish'

But there is no influence on the stress pattern of the host.

Finally, there are suffixes bearing a main stress and those get the main stress of the whole thing:

/-ə'ri/ ˈ-ing (n)'
 /-'ɛs/ ˈf'
 /-'m/ ˈf'
 /-'ɛi/ ˈ-ship'

[.,ʔɛ.tə.'ri.] ˈeating (n)'
 [vo:g.'d+ɛs.] ˈfem. guardian' (b.th.w.: no final devoicing in this example, because of regressive voicing assimilation, Booij 1995:59)

[.hɛl.'d+m.] ˈheroine'
 [vo:g.'d+ɛi.] ˈguardianship'

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

Only native, strong inflected verb stems undergo ablaut within their inflection, so this process is not important for word domains. There are no affixes that cause ablaut.

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

As it is usual in Germanic languages, Dutch has strong and weak forms of pronouns, articles, some adverbs, adpositions and some auxiliary forms. The weak forms cliticize to the previous pword (as first word of a sentence, they cliticize to the following word). In this process, all resyllabification and morphophonemic rules apply:

(zɛi)_ω((kɔx)_σ(tə)_σ(n=ət)_σ(buk)_ω ˈThey bought the book.'

Since the clitic forms contain either schwa or no vowel at all (three clitics have [i] or [ɪ]), they cannot be stressed.

To resolve an occurring hiatus after schwa, an [n] can be inserted (this rule only applies within pwords!) or the schwa can be deleted (as it is the case in pwords normally):

(.vɪl.də.ni.)_ω ˈwanted (/vɪldə/) he'
 ət(xɛ.kə.nɪs)_ω ~ ət(xɛ.kɪs)_ω ~ ət(xɛ.kə)_ω(ʔɪs)_ω ˈthe strange thing (/ʔɛkə/) is'

If the clitic is the first word of a sentence, no [n] can be inserted:

jə=(ʔe:t)_ω (*jəne:t) 'you eat'

In this case the clitic is not part of the pword, to which it is attached. (This is the same behaviour as the schwa containing prefixes show.)

If sentence-initial, the clitics [t=] 'it' and [k=] 'I' form consonant clusters that do not occur lexically:

[txa:t] (t=(xa:t)_ω) 'it goes'
[ksal] (k=(sal)_ω) 'I will'

Final Devoicing does take place, even when vowel-initial enclitics are there and a resyllabification does occur:

/vənd/ + /ɪk/ → [ˌvɒn.t=ɪk.] 'found I'

With very frequent verbs, FD does sometimes not occur:

/hɛb/ + /ɪk/ → [ˌhɛ.bɪk.] ~ [ˌhɛ.pɪk.] 'have I'

Voicing assimilation takes place with both proclitics and enclitics and both progressive and regressive:

ət=(xɛ.kə)_ω 'the strange thing (/ɣɛkə/)
əɖ=(bɔz=ɪn)_ω 'into the wood (/bɔs/)

The last consonant of a word and even the schwa of the clitic can be deleted before the clitics [jə] 'you.sg' and [k] 'I':

(vɪl + jə) → [vɪj(ə)] 'want you'
(vɪl + k) → [vɪk] 'want I'
(kən + jə) → [kɔj(ə)] 'can you'
(mu:t + jə) → [mu:j(ə)] 'must you'
(mu:t + k) → [mu:k] 'must I'
(hɛb + jə) → [hɛj(ə)] 'have you'
(hɛb + k) → [hɛk] 'have I'
(məɪ + k) → [mɔk] 'may I'

but no contraction in:

(kən + k) → [kən̩k] 'can I'
(məɪ + jə) → [məɪjə] 'may you'

The verbs for 'to have' and 'to be' can contract with proclitics:

((ʔɪ)k + hɛb) → [(ʔɪ)kɛp] 'I have'
(hɛɪ + hɛ:ft) → [hɛɪft] 'he has'
(zə + hɛ:ft) → [zɛ:ft] 'she has'
(və + hɛbən) → [vɛbən] 'we have'
(hɛɪ + ʔɪs) → [hɛɪs] 'he is'
(dət + ʔɪs) → [dɔs] 'that is'
(vət + ʔɪs + dət) → [vɔzɔt] ~ [vɔstɔt] 'what is that'

Possible phonetic realizations of a complex clitic cluster (the stem is marked bold):

/ɪk + **hɛb** + ət + əm/ [ɣəze:ɣət]
I have it him told
'I have told it to him.'

[ʔɪk **hɛp**=ət=əm]
[ʔɪk **hɛp**=t=əm]
[ʔɪk=**ɛp**=ət=əm]
[ʔɪk=**ɛp**=t=əm]

[k=ɛp=ət=əm]
[k=ɛp=t=əm]

VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

Diversions in phonological processes:

A *Phonotactics*: No diversions found.

B *Phonological processes*: In the following part I list all processes with their domains (provided that I can examine, which it is), independent whether or not there are diversions among the grammatical morphemes (for an overview of the phonological rules).

Domain abbreviations:

μ mora
σ syllable
φ foot
ω phonological word
Φ phonological phrase
IP intonational phrase
U utterance

1. Devoicing: [-son] → [-voiced] / ___C₀²)_σ (domain: σ)

/madrɪd/ → [madrɪt] 'Madrid' (no devoicing of the first /d/, because it belongs to the second syllable)

Since the Final Devoicing rule is syllable based, it does also occur with affixes and in compounds. But: The rule also applies in compounds and cliticized forms, even when resyllabification occurs:

/vɔnd=ɪk/ → [vɔn.t=ɪk.] 'found I'

2. Regressive Voicing Assimilation: [-son] → [+voiced] / ___[-son, -cont, +voiced] (domain: ω, optionally Φ)

Between the parts of a compound or with clitics, the rule is only optional:

(vat + ʔɪs + dat) → [vazdat] ~ [vastat] 'what is that'

3. Progressive Voicing Assimilation: [-son, +cont] → [-voiced] / [-son, -voiced]___ (domain: IP(!))

/stra:t+ɣo:t/ (compound) → [stra:tɣo:t] 'gutter'
/də##rand##van/ → [də##rɔnt##fɔn] 'the edge of'

No diversions found.

Thus, the rules 1-3 are ordered: 1 > 2 > 3.

4. Nasal assimilation: [CORONAL, +nas] → [αPLACE] / ___[αPLACE, +cons] (domain: IP)

/a:n+bɔd/ → [ʔa:mbɔt] 'offer'
/ɪn##madrɪd/ → [ɪnmadrɪt] 'in Madrid' (additionally: degemination)
/ɔn+vast/ → [ʔɔŋvast] 'unstable'
/ɪn##jy:li/ → [ɪnjy:li] 'in July'
/ɔn+kɪs/ → [ʔɔŋkɪs] 'indecent'
/...ba:n##kreɪt/ → [...ba:ŋ##kreɪt] 'job gets'

No diversions found.

5. Glottal stop epenthesis: ∅ → [ʔ] / {[+low], ω}{___φ}([DORS, -cons]) (domain: φ)

/aɔrta/ → [(ʔa)_φ(ʔɔrta)_φ] 'aorta'

but:
/xɑos/ → [(xɑos)_φ] 'chaos'

Pword-initial: With stress-bearing affixes or in compounds the rule can optionally be replaced by the glide epenthesis rule (6), when the first part ends in a vowel except [a].

/ku+ɑxtəy/ → [ku:ʔɑxtəx] ~ [ku:vɑxtəx] 'cow-like'
/ze:#a:rənd/ → [ze:ʔa:rənt] ~ [ze:ja:rənt] 'sea eagle'

6. Glide epenthesis: Ø → [j] / [-low, -round, -back]___[DORS, -cons]
→ [ɥ] / [-low, +round, -back]___[DORS, -cons]
→ [v] / [-low, +back]___[DORS, -cons] (domain: IP)

see 5.

/mari:#e:t/ → [mari:#j#e:t] 'Mary eats'

7. Schwa deletion: /ə/ → Ø / ___[DORS, -cons] (domain: ω, and in casual speech IP)

/elitə+ɛr/ → [ʔelitɛ:r] 'elitist'
/ka:də+ən/ → [ka:dən] 'quays'
but:
/bə+antvɔ:rdən/ → [bəʔantvɔ:rdən] 'reply.INF'
/zeidə+ɑxtəy/ → [zeidəʔɑxtəx] 'silk-like'
but again (in casual speech):
/də=a:vənd/ → [dɑ:vənt] 'the evening'
/ro:d+ə#a:rdbɛij+ən/ → [ro:d#a:rtbɛijən] 'red strawberries'

Thus, the rules 5-7 are ordered: 5 > 7 > 6.

8. Degemination: [+cons]_α → Ø / ___[+cons]_α (domain: ω, optionally IP)

/e:t+t/ → [ʔe:t] 'eat.3sPRS'
/yə+vud+d/ → [yəvu:t] 'feed.PT.PTCP'
/ɔn+mɪdəl+lək/ → [ʔɔmɪdələk] 'immediately' (additional: nasal assimilation)
but:
/vɛr+rasən/ → [vɛr(r)asən] 'surprise.INF'
/jan##nɑm/ → [ja(n)##nɑm] 'John took'

Thus, rules 4 and 8 are ordered: 4 > 8.

9. d-Insertion: Ø → [d] / [r]___ər (domain: at least ω)

/bitər+ər/ → [bitərdər] 'more bitter'
/klir+ərɛi/ → [klirdərəi] 'nagging'

I did not find out, what happens in compounds with ...rə##r...

10. a:-Insertion: Ø → [a:] / ə [+son, CORONAL]_ω ___ [r] (domain: ω)
(Thereafter the Schwa deletion rule has to apply! The inserted [a:] gets secondary stress!)

/asən+ər/ → [ʔasəna:r] 'inhabitant of the town of Assen'
but:
/heikəl+ər/ → [heikələr] 'riskier'

!! This should show that the domain is ω, and the de-nominal suffix -ər is different from the COMP-suffix -ər in their pword-coherence. Booij wrote, that the underlying form is /-ər/ in both cases, but I think that the de-nominal suffix has underlying /-ar/ instead. The vowel is lengthened if stressed (this is the normal lengthening rule), and reduced to schwa if unstressed (this is an unstressed vowel reduction rule that also occurs in other contexts in the language). So rule 10 is likely no phonological rule of Dutch.

11. Schwa-deletion in medieval Dutch: /ə/ → Ø / [-son, +voiced]___ω (domain: ω)

/e:ndə/ → [ʔe:nt] 'end' (more formal: [ʔe:ndə])
/kø:zə/ → [kø:s] 'choice' (more formal: [kø:zə])

No diversions found.

12. /də/-deletion in medieval Dutch: /də/ → Ø / [-cons]___{#, [-cons]} (domain: ω)

/la:də/ → [la:] 'drawer' (more formal: [la:də])
/bru:dər/ → [bru:r] 'brother' (more formal: [bru:dər])

No diversions found.

13. Labial fricative devoicing before [-ələk] and [-ənɪs]: /v/ → [f] / ___+{[-ələk], [-ənɪs]}

/ɣra:v+ələk/ → [ɣra:fələk] 'of a court'
/la:v+ənɪs/ → [la:fənɪs] 'refreshment'

14. Coronal fricative devoicing before [-ələk]: /z/ → [s] / ___+[-ələk]

/vre:z+ələk/ → [vre:sələk] 'horrible'

15. Palatalizing: [CORONAL, -cont] → [-anterior] / ___j (domain: IP)

/tas+jə/ → [tʃjə] 'bag.DIM'
/hand+jə/ → [hɑŋtʃjə] ~ [hɑŋtjə] 'hand.DIM'
/sja:l/ → [ʃja:l] 'shawl'
/ik=kɛn##jə=mu:dər/ → [ʔikɛŋ##jəmu:dər] 'I know your mother'

No diversions found.

16. Schwa deletion: /ə/ → Ø / .[+cons]___.[+son, +cons, -nas]ə (This rule is only optional!) (domain: ω)

/knəbəl+ən/ → [knəb(ə)lən] 'munch.INF'
/ɣəmək+ələk/ → [ɣəmək(ə)lək] 'easy'

No diversions found.

17. Vowel reduction: [DORS, -cons, -stress, -long] → [ə] / [-asp]___C₀ⁿ (X₀ⁿ)₀ (This rule is only optional!) (domain: Φ)

/bana:n/ → [bəna:n] ~ [bana:n] 'banana'
/myzi:k/ → [məzi:k] ~ [myzi:k] 'music'
but:
/eli:tə/ → [ʔeli:tə] 'elite'
/hyma:n/ → [hyma:n] 'human (adj)'
/seizu:n/ → [seizu:n] 'season'

No diversions found.

This rule has to apply before the Glottal Stop Epenthesis (rule 5).

18. Schwa insertion: Ø → [ə] / [αPLACE]___[βPLACE]₀ (α↔β) (This rule is only optional!) (domain: σ)
(The syllable boundary also excludes appendix consonants for the second one!)

/kalm/ → [kal(ə)m] 'quiet'
/markt/ → [mar(ə)kt] 'market'
but: *[markət] 'market'

No diversions found.

19. /n/-deletion: /n/ → ∅ / ə____o (This rule is only optional!) (domain: σ)

/re:yən/ → [re:yə(n)] 'rain'
 /blu:m+ən/ → [blu:mə(n)] 'flower.PL'
 /e:t+ən/ → [ʔe:tə(n)] 'eat.INF'
 /zɛt+ən/ → [zɛtə(n)] 'put.PRS.PL'
 but:
 /zɛt+ən=ət/ → [zɛtənət] 'put.PRS.PL=it'

No diversions found.

20. /i/-deletion: /i/[-stressed] → ∅ / ([-stressed])_{oo}(C)___j (This rule is only optional!) (domain: Φ)
 (Before this rule can apply, the Glide Insertion (rule 6) has to take place!)

/pia:no/ → [p(i)ja:no] 'piano'
 /sosi+a:l/ → [so(i)ja:l] 'social'

No diversions found.

21. /t/-deletion: /t/ → ∅ / [-son]___[-syllab] / [+son, +cons]___[-son (except [k])] (domain: ω, optionally Φ)
 / [-son]___[-son] (this is only an optional rule, the domain is IP!)

/klaxt+tjə/ → [klaxjə] 'complaint.DIM'
 /ɛxt+st/ → [ʔɛxst] 'most real'
 /ɔnt+plɔfən/ → [ʔɔmplɔfən] 'explode.INF'
 /pɔst+kanto:r/ → [pɔs(t)kanto:r] 'post office'
 but:
 /hart+tjə/ → [hartjə] 'heart.DIM'
 /bɔnt+kra:y/ → [bɔntkra:x] 'fur collar'
 /kɔmt+pi:t/ → [kɔm(t)pi:t] 'Does Peter come?'

No diversions found.

C Other allomorphies

1. Vowel backing and stress-shift in non-native suffixes:
 [-cons, -high, -low] → [+back, -stress] / +[___[+cons]]_s+ [X]_s (both S(uffixes) are non-native!):

/mor+e:l/ → [more:l] 'moral'
 /mor+e:l+ismə/ → [mɔrəlɪsmə] 'moralism'
 /dirɛkt+ø:r/ → [dirɛktø:r] 'director'
 /dirɛkt+ø:r+a:t/ → [dirɛktɔrɑ:t] 'directorship'

2. Nasal assimilation in non-native prefixes:

/n/ → [αPLACE] / ___+[αPLACE, -son]
 ∅ / ___+[+cons, +son]

/in+populɛ:r/ → [ʔɪmpopulɛ:r] 'unpopular'
 /kɔn+kla:f/ → [kɔŋkla:f] 'conclave'
 /in+leɪa:l/ → [ʔɪleɪa:l] 'illegal'
 /in+tolerant/ → [ʔɪntolerant] 'intolerant'

3. /a:-/ → [ʔan-] / ___[DORS, -cons]

/a:+oryɑ:nɪs/ → [ʔanʔoryɑ:nɪs] 'inorganic' (I'm not sure, whether or not the glottal stop epenthesis applies to the stem.)

4. /de:-/ → [dɛs-] / ___[DORS, -cons]

/de:+ɪntərəsə/ → [dɛsʔɪntərəsə] 'disinterest' (dito)

5. /t/-spirantization before certain suffixes in non-native words:

/t/ → [s] / [+cons]___+(i)jV}
[ts] / [-cons]___+(i)jV}

/akt+i/ → [ʔaksi] 'action'

/kant+ija:n/ → [kansija:n] 'Kantian'

/ra:t+iʝo/ → [ra:tsiʝo] 'ratio'

/president+je:l/ → [presidentʃje:l] 'presidential' (palatalizing rule see 15. above)

but:

/akt+if/ → [ʔakti:f] 'active'

6. Vowel lengthening before vowel-initial suffixes in non-native words:

[-cons, -stressed] → [+long] / ___[+cons]+[-cons]

/ne:pal+e:s/ → [nepa:le:s] 'Nepalese'

/doktər+a:t/ → [dokto:ra:t] 'doctorate'

Bipartite stems: Not attested.

IX Reduplication

not attested

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

Phrase intonation: Stress hierarchy is: N, V > A > Adv > Function words
clause and sentence levels: The main stress is on the focussed phrase.

Phrase stress shifts: If a main stress of a word gets into a position next to the main stress of another word within a phrase (there may be unstressed syllables in between!), the first is deleted or, if there is no secondary stress left of it, changed into a secondary stress and shifted left as far as possible. There is no shift, if the stressed syllable of the first word is preceded by a single unstressed syllable.

Stress deletion:

[.,do:d.'zi:k.] 'seriously ill'
[.,do:d.zi:k##'kɪnt.] 'seriously ill child'

[.,ʔɒn.də.'ra:n.] 'at the foot of'
[.,ʔɒn.də.ra:n##də='be:rɪx.] 'at the foot of the mountain'

Stress weakening and shift:

[.spe.ʃi.'ja:l.] 'special'
[.spe.ʃi.ja:l##'ʝə.'va:l.] 'special case'

Stress weakening without shift:

[.ba.'na:l] 'banal'
[.ba.,na:l##'ʝrɒp.jə.] 'banal joke'

Pause phenomena: I have not found anything like this.

Special phenomena: None.

XI Other Special things

Geminates: see phonological rule 8 (Geminate deletion) above (in section VII)

Foot: e.g. see phonological rule 5 (Glottal Stop Epenthesis) above (in section VII)